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Conference Paper · May 2023

DOI: 10.1109/IPDPSW59300.2023.00062

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Toward a Modular Workflow for Network Performance Characterization

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Abstract—In this work, we propose the Network Performance Collector (NPC) workflow for automated network performance characterization. The workflow relies on the collection, processing, and visualization of network performance metrics such as throughput and latency, and can be used for analysis with various network performance models. Depending on the selected model, benchmark tools such as *iperf* or *sockperf* and microbenchmarks specific to parallel programming models can be automated and orchestrated for data collection using the NPC. The data obtained can then be used by NPC to, for example, validate and characterize the performance of the underlying network or to analyze the system limitations for a given application.

Index Terms—Network interconnects, Automated Performance Characterization, Roofline Model, HPC

I. INTRODUCTION

There are several ways to determine the actual performance metrics of a point-to-point link for a given interconnection network. Well-known tools such as *qperf* [1] or *sockperf* [2] offer various network benchmarks to determine concrete values for, for example, the throughput or latency of a connection. As with most benchmarks, the reproducibility of the results and the observed performance depends on the selected parameter settings and the execution environment. Network benchmark tools offer a wide range of different options depending on the network technology and protocol, but are commonly based on the client-server model, i.e. it is necessary to use different parameters for server and client side. This circumstance makes it difficult to perform such benchmarks on supercomputers where workload managers such as Slurm are used. In addition, microbenchmarks for parallel programming models such as MPI can provide an estimate for the network performance observed by applications. Although it is possible to obtain an interactive shell, it would be more convenient and user-oriented to run these benchmarks as simple, automated jobs that can be scheduled by the workload manager.

To address these shortcomings, we propose the preliminary *Network Performance Collector* (NPC) workflow to ensure reproducibility, comparability, and portability of the obtained results. With NPC it is possible to automate the benchmarking process and easily obtain performance data for different subsets of the available benchmark configurations. The modularity of its design allows NPC to be configured and applied to different network performance models, such as the Roofline model [3]. The goal is to develop a tool chain for automating the characterization of modern HPC systems, with particular

regard to the increasingly heterogeneous (network) infrastructure. One example is the *Modular Supercomputer Architecture* (MSA) [4], which leverages a system design that is based on heterogeneous hardware modules instead of the traditional homogeneous, fat-node approach. MSA systems consist of multiple modules, including a general-purpose CPU cluster, an accelerator-based Booster cluster (e.g. GPUs), or a quantum computing module as independent compute resources. The modularity of these components also affects the deployed network technologies, i.e. each module could use a different technology such as InfiniBand or Ethernet. In this context, a workflow for network performance modeling and automated system characterization will be even more important.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In the following, we provide a brief overview of selected state-of-the-art network benchmark tools and their features. We also briefly discuss relevant work in the area of performance modeling, in particular the Roofline model.

A. Network Benchmarks

qperf [1] can be used to measure the throughput and latency between two nodes for the *Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol* (TCP/IP) and *Remote Direct Memory Access* (RDMA). A convenient aspect of *qperf* is that the number of different benchmarks that are run sequentially can be defined without having to restart the client or server. *sockperf* [2] can be used to measure throughput and latency via the Socket API. RDMA communication can only be evaluated by using *Socket Direct Protocol* (SDP) or *Internet Protocol over Infiniband* (IPoIB). *hpcbench* [5] is an older project specifically designed to provide benchmarks for what were then considered high-performance networking technologies, including Myrinet, Gigabit Ethernet, and QsNet. *perftest* [6] consists of several independent benchmarks specifically designed to evaluate RDMA-based communication using Verbs. Tools such as *iperf3*, *netperf*, and *nuttcp* can also be used to evaluate TCP/IP-based networks. Due to the brevity of this work, these cannot be further discussed here.

B. Performance Models

A recent survey [7] has summarized an overview of state-of-the-art analytical communication performance models. In contrast, the Roofline model [3] is intuitive and can be used

to estimate the performance of a given processor along with off-chip memory traffic. Essentially, it is a two dimensional graph showing the *operational intensity*, also referred to as the *arithmetical intensity*, on the x-axis and the floating point performance on the y-axis. The main objective is to set upper limits on the attainable floating point performance and DRAM bandwidth to characterize the performance of a given machine. Using these upper bounds, applications can be categorized as *memory-bound* or *compute-bound* depending on their position within the model. Optimal performance is achieved when the application can neither be classified as compute-bound nor memory-bound. An extension of the Roofline model is also possible, e.g. for computing cores running on a GPU. The PCIe bandwidth can also be a useful additional upper bound, as it defines the upper limit for the speed of data transfers between host and device memory. In addition, for distributed programs, the attainable bandwidth of interconnection networks can be used as another upper bound [8]. We intend to automate a preliminary extension of the traditional Roofline model for network performance characterization in this work.

III. NETWORK PERFORMANCE COLLECTOR (NPC) WORKFLOW FOR METRIC EVALUATION

Our paper proposes the design of an automated workflow for network performance benchmarking and characterization and metrics evaluation, as shown in Figure 1.

A. Workflow Design

The *Network Performance Collector* (NPC) workflow can be divided in several phases. Prior to Phase 1 *Benchmark and Metric Identification*, a suitable *Network Performance Model* needs to be selected, depending on the performance aspect or system behavior (e.g. speed, bandwidth, access latency) to be analyzed. It is important to note that this step defines at least a subset of the information needed for Phase 1. In the future, we plan to include the network performance model selection as Phase 0 by providing a predefined set of performance models. Depending on the chosen model, in Phase 1, the metrics of interest need to be defined as well as the benchmark and parameter set. This decision must also be made with respect to the given network technology. In addition, it makes sense to use further microbenchmarks for parallel programming models such as MPI or Partitioned Global Address Space (PGAS). These reflect the observed communication performance at application level. The next step is Phase 2 *Automation*, i.e. the orchestration and execution of the benchmark set. Subsequently, in Phase 3 *Performance Modeling*, the extraction of the corresponding benchmark results from the generated output is performed and prepared for further processing. In Phase 4 *Result Visualization*, all produced benchmark results are transformed to a suitable presentation format, e.g. a plot, a table or a csv file. Depending on the user-defined settings, Phases 2 and 3 can be executed multiple times in an iterative manner. Including time as an additional dimension, Phase 4 then can provide insight into an application’s performance over time, enabling the identification and understanding of

Fig. 1: Overview of the NPC workflow.

performance anomalies. Finally, the findings and insights of the performance analysis and characterization can be used to perform *Network Tuning and Optimization*, for example to change the network settings or communication behavior of a certain application. If further analysis is required, the NPC workflow can be performed again.

B. Prototype Implementation

The NPC workflow implementation is based on the *JUBE* benchmarking environment [9]. *JUBE* provides a script-based framework specifically to create and automate benchmark sets, and to provide reproducible and comparable results across runs on different computer systems, i.e. portability. *JUBE*-based workflows can either be written in YAML or XML. Our prototype implementation currently covers Phases 2 and 3, as shown in Figure 1. We exploit *JUBE*’s ability to execute shell commands directly, which makes it easy to submit jobs with different parameters and configurations to the system’s workload manager. All steps defined in *JUBE* run inside their own work directory. To collect results from different directories, the NPC implementation uses *JUBE*’s *Analysis Module*, which provides a custom set of benchmark-specific regular expressions to extract the desired values from the results files. After the extraction, the collected results can be displayed and saved to a file inside the work directory. For demonstration purposes, we have implemented two scripts in R to visualize the results. Examples are provided in Section IV.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL USE CASES

In this section, we present two use cases for our NPC implementation. The first consists of a bandwidth analysis with different network benchmarks and MPI implementations. Then, we employ the NPC to apply the Roofline model for given applications. Both examples can be seen as preliminary work in automated network performance characterization.

We used the *FUCHS-CSC Cluster* at Goethe University Frankfurt as a testbed. It consists of 190 identical nodes each equipped with 2x Intel Xeon E5-2670 v2 (Ivy Bridge) with 128 GB of RAM and FDR InfiniBand.

A. Network Performance Benchmark (NPB)

Complementing our proposed NPC workflow, we introduce the Python-based *Network Performance Benchmark* (NPB) as part of Phase 2, which addresses the shortcomings introduced

Fig. 2: Comparison between the benchmarks qperf and sockperf and the MPI implementations OpenMPI and MVAPICH2.

by typical network benchmarks such as qperf or sockperf in terms of automation. In place of real applications, NPB can be used as a synthetic workload in the NPC workflow. NPB takes a variety of command line arguments to properly orchestrate the given benchmark. The creation of processes is done with the help of *mpi4py*. The use of MPI facilitates the creation of separate processes for server and client on remote compute nodes. NPB checks at startup if the correct number of processes is requested, otherwise the program is terminated. Furthermore, it identifies the hostname of the server automatically, which makes it easy to use in conjunction with workload managers on HPC systems such as Slurm.

1) *Experimental Setup:* To test the applicability of our NPB implementation, we have defined an experimental environment in which we want to study the performance of different benchmarks and compare them with each other. We chose qperf and sockperf as low-level network benchmarks because both are capable of providing results for Gigabit Ethernet (GigE) and InfiniBand. In addition, we used the OSU Micro-Benchmarks (OMB) [10] to provide a comparison with the performance results of MPI-based point-to-point communication. Here we also compare the performance of two different MPI implementations with each other, namely *MVAPICH2* [11] and *OpenMPI* [12]. The benchmark runs were conducted for message sizes from 16 to 32768 bytes.

2) *Results:* Figure 2 depicts the results for GigE (upper plot) and FDR InfiniBand (lower plot). As can be seen, the performance achieved with qperf and sockperf is quite similar for GigE. The throughput delivered by the MPI benchmarks also reaches peak performance, but only for message sizes of 4096 bytes and larger. Both qperf and sockperf perform measurements for a fixed period of time, e.g. 1 second. During this time, the client sends as many messages as possible, so the network reaches its saturation point much earlier. The

TABLE I: Benchmark configuration.

Benchmark	#Nodes	#Process	#OMPThreads	Precision
HimenoXL	2	8	/	Single
HimenoXL	4	64	/	Single
HPCG	2	4	40	Double
HPCG	4	8	80	Double

OMB does not run for a specific time, but sends a defined number of messages. This number is called the window size and has a default value of 64. The observation is the same for both network technologies and can be explained by the large difference in message rates. A closer look at the FDR InfiniBand results reveals the poor performance of sockperf. As mentioned in Section II-A, sockperf can only be used with the Socket API. Thus, the results shown were obtained with IPOIB, which is likely to perform the worst in this case.

B. Roofline Model Analysis

1) *Machine Characterization:* We used qperf to determine an upper ceiling for the attainable network bandwidth. The measurement was performed for a reliable connected queue pair. For the floating point ceiling of the used processor, the *Likwid Performance Tools* [13] were applied. The peak *Floating Point Operations per Second* (FLOPS) were measured with the `likwid-bench -t peakflops_avx -W N:400kB:40` benchmark configuration for single and double precision, respectively.

2) *Application Benchmarks and Experimental Setup:* We used the well-known *Himeno* [14] and *High Performance Conjugate Gradients* (HPCG) [15] benchmarks to test the proposed workflow and evaluate the application of the Roofline model. Both benchmarks use MPI to leverage the single program multiple data (SPMD) paradigm and report the FLOPS achieved as benchmark results. Since we are interested in the network performance, we have to measure the number of received and transmitted bytes. For this task, both benchmarks were modified to support the *Performance Application Programming Interface* (PAPI) [16]. PAPI provides access to hardware performance counters for the CPU as well as for the NIC. Using PAPI’s low-level API, it is possible to track the amount of bytes transferred per node.

For the roofline, we define the following equation:

$$P = \min(P_{peak}, I \cdot b_s)$$

where P_{peak} is the attainable floating point performance in FLOPS and the slope is given by

$$I \cdot b_s = \frac{FLOP}{network\ byte} \cdot \frac{byte}{s}$$

where I corresponds to the operational intensity and b_s is the attainable network bandwidth. Figure 3 shows the Roofline model for a single node of the system used, i.e., the results were downsampled to reflect the performance results at the node level regardless of the number of processes. The benchmark configuration can be seen in Table I. For the Himeno benchmark, we used the “static allocation, MPI” implementation without employing additional threads and did

Fig. 3: Roofline model with Himeno and HPCG results.

not provide any hints for process binding. HPCG has been configured to use MPI for inter-node communication and OpenMP for multithreading at the node-level. Here, we used the `-map-by ppr:1:socket` option provided by OpenMPI’s `mpirun` implementation to launch exactly one MPI process per available socket. For the OpenMP threads, we used the `OMP_PLACES=cores` environment variable to control the location where threads are launched. Our test machine offers ten cores per socket, thus we chose to spawn 10 threads per socket and map them respectively.

The Himeno benchmark needs to be configured with a fixed problem size, i.e. running with an increasing number of processes shows strong scaling behavior. HPCG adjusts the total problem size depending on the number of processes started, while the local problem size remains the same for each process, leading to weak scaling results.

Figure 3 depicts the resulting Roofline model including the benchmark results. The results show that both problems are *computation bound* and are not affected by the available network performance. As expected, the operational intensity decreases by a factor of two when the number of nodes is doubled. The increase in processes and nodes also leads to more network communication, which pushes the point further to the upper boundary of network bandwidth when the number of nodes is four. The *ridge point* for the current system would require an operational intensity of 60 *FLOP / network byte* and a floating point performance of about 412 *GFLOPS* for double precision or about 820 *GFLOPS* for single precision.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In summary, the proposed workflow can be considered as a template for our future work in performance analysis and characterization. In addition, there are several aspects of network performance metrics, such as network efficiency, for which we intend to build an extended Roofline model. Unfortunately, the Roofline model does not take latency aspects into account. Therefore, we plan to investigate different techniques for modeling latency, for which we will use the data collected by

NPC. We also plan to compare our approach to existing work in the areas of simulation, machine learning, and analytical methods for performance estimation. Beyond that, our work is part of a project to evaluate and combine network performance, machine utilization and performance metrics, and I/O-related metrics into a unified performance model. Further information, including all scripts used in this work, is available on our GitHub companion page: <https://github.com/msqc-goethe/npc>.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research is supported by EUPEX, which has received funding from the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under GA No 101033975. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, France, Germany, Italy, Greece, United Kingdom, Czech Republic, and Croatia.

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